

CBSE senior secondary school students awareness and practices of safety measures in Chemistry laboratory

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Abstract

This study investigated the current status of awareness and practices of safety measures in senior secondary school Chemistry laboratory in Varanasi city. The descriptive survey method was used at three schools with a sample size of 275 students. A self-made questionnaire was used to collect data which were analysed using inferential statistics mean, SD and T test. Additionally, through self-made observation schedule practices of safety measures was observed. The result shows that Awareness of safety measures in Chemistry laboratory was found to be low. The practices of safety measures adopted by Senior Secondary school students revealed poor experimental techniques. It was found that senior secondary school students has poor knowledge about identify emergency facility and equipment.

Introduction

What is science science is understanding of natural world derived from act discovered via experimentation and observation .In other words a discipline that focus on the natural world as Biology physics or chemistry . science is a subject that is formally studied. In school science curriculum mainly study physics chemistry and Biology. What is chemistry? Chemistry is a branch of science that studies the makeup,structure and characteristic of substances as well as changes they go through. In other words the study of composition structure characteristics and change of matter that focus in the field of physical science known as chemistry. In Chemistry lab work is important to gain knowledge about matter, its composition and transformation

.What is Chemistry laboratory is a room or a structure in school used for conducting scientific experiment analysis and research. Why laboratory work is important in Chemistry. since chemistry is a laboratory based subject. It cannot be taught to pupils in middle or high School without adequate laboratory exposure .The subject includes the identification,manipulation, general usages of laboratory equipment, equipment for meaningful demonstration and experimentation should be available in school lab . All students must be able to access the lab

environments, which must also be kept in a safe condition .During any investigation teacher should take precautions, teacher should take precautions to keep both themselves and their children safe.Students with restricted strength or mobility can participate in lab experience with the proper modifications. The best way to make sure a students acquire fundamental scientific abilities is thought instruction that is a student centred and highlights the important of laboratory demonstration and experiments . laboratory work follow the principal of learning by doing, learning by experience, learning by activity that is one of the basic principle of learning. In laboratory students get opportunity to be active participant in the learning process the knowledge constructed through experimental work or activity create permanent Impressions in the mind of students .Practical work gives the student an opportunity to develop skills like handling different equipment (tongs, spatulas , pipette), drawing diagrams and integrating results . The students by interaction learn to be Cooperative resourceful and collaborative self discipline self reliant quality which carry over day- to- day living. The students get ample training in scientific method several problems crop up during laboratory work , project work and activity which the students learn to deal with and solve.The students gradually develop a scientific attitude and scientific out look, a major objective in teaching of chemistry.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the status of safety provision in the Chemistry laboratory in senior secondary school?
2. What is the level of awareness of senior secondary school students regarding safety measures in the Chemistry laboratory?
3. What are practices of safety measures adopted by senior secondary school students in the Chemistry laboratory?

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study of CBSE senior secondary school student's awareness and practices of safety measures in the Chemistry laboratory.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF KEY WORDS

1. **Awareness of safety measures** – Awareness of safety measures, in this study, means knowledge of dangers frequently occurring in the Chemistry laboratory, knowledge of how to avoid or prevent danger and knowledge of steps to be taken after an incident. It was measured using the ‘Chemistry Laboratory safety Skills Questionnaire’

developed by the researcher. The score obtained on this questionnaire were considered as the measure of awareness of safety measures.

2. **Practices of safety measures-** Practices of safety measures refers to use of knowledge about precaution while working in the laboratory. Example - Handling of glass ware and chemicals; use of apron; goggles; gloves and shoes; washing hands before leaving lab; use of first aid kits in the lab etc. For the purpose of study practices of safety measures were assessed using the observation schedule for the practices of safety measures developed by the researcher.
3. **Infrastructural Provisions for Safety measures in Chemistry laboratory-** Safety measures in Chemistry laboratory refers to presence of proper infrastructure (good ventilation, clear exit, spacious lab desk etc), proper pipe line facilities, proper handling of chemicals, glass ware, burner etc, knowledge of the location of all safety equipment (fire extinguisher), proper waste disposal system in the lab etc. For the purpose of study safety measures in Chemistry laboratory were assessed using the observation schedule for infrastructural provisions for safety measures in the chemistry laboratory developed by the researcher.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

MAIN OBJECTIVE

1. To observe the provisions for safety in the Chemistry laboratory in comparison to the recommended CBSE norms.
2. To assess the level of awareness of safety measures of senior secondary school students in the Chemistry laboratory.
3. To observe the practices of safety measures adopted by senior secondary school students while doing practical in the Chemistry laboratory.

SUBSIDIARY OBJECTIVES

1. To compare the awareness about the lab safety measures of male and female senior secondary students.
2. To compare the awareness about the lab safety measures of senior secondary students of class XI and XII.

CONCOMITANT OBJECTIVES

1. To develop observation schedule on Infrastructural provisions for safety in the Chemistry laboratory.
2. To develop the questionnaire to assess the level of awareness of safety measures of senior secondary school students in the Chemistry laboratory.

3. To develop an observation schedule for observation of safety measures practices adopted by senior secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significance difference between the level of awareness about the lab safety measures of male and female senior secondary students.
2. There is no significance difference between the level of awareness about the lab safety measures of senior secondary students of class XIth and XIIth.

DELIMITATIONS

This study would be limited to the students studying in the senior secondary schools of Varanasi District only.

In the present study only the norm led by CBSE will be taken under consideration for comparison.

RESEARCH METHOD:

The present study was carried out by utilizing the descriptive survey method. Survey is an important method, which involves a clearly defined problem and definite objectives. It also requires experts and imaginative planning, careful analysis and interpretation of data collected and logical and skillful reporting of the findings.

POPULATION:

All senior secondary science students of class XI and XII of CBSE affiliated schools of Varanasi district.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Cluster Random Sampling was used for the selection of sample.

SAMPLE:

Students of Science section of class 11th & 12th from Varanasi Public School, Central Hindu Girls School and Swami Harsevanand Public School were selected for the sample.

SCHOOL NAME & NUMBER OF SAMPLE:

NAME OF THE SCHOOL	NUMBER OF SAMPLE
Varanasi Public School	148
Central Hindu Girls School	33
Swami Harsevanand Public School	94

Total number of male sample taken for this study was 162 and total number of female sample taken for this study was 113.

TOOL:

For this study the researcher developed three tools in the guidance of supervisor namely; Chemistry Laboratory Safety Skills Questionnaire, Observation Schedule for Practices of Safety Measures and Observation Schedule for Infrastructural Provisions for Safety Measures in the Chemistry Laboratory.

OBSERVATION OF PROVISIONS FOR SAFETY IN THE CHEMISTRY LABORATORY:

The first objective of the study was to observe the provisions for safety in the Chemistry laboratory in comparison to the recommended CBSE norms.

For the above purpose the researcher observed three schools Central Hindu Girls School, Varanasi Public School and Swami Harsevanand Public School with the help of ‘Observation Schedule for Infrastructural Provisions for Safety Measures in the Chemistry Laboratory’ developed by the researcher. This tool was developed in accordance to the norms laid down by the CBSE board. The Observation Schedule was divided into 4 domains namely-

1. Physical Facilities
2. Lab Equipment
3. Teacher’s monitoring and student’s behavior
4. Safety equipment’s

DOMAIN WISE DESCRIPTION OF OBSERVATION:**Physical Facilities:**

1. CHGS has proper infrastructure i.e. only one school has proper infrastructural facility.
2. All three schools have well lighted, well ventilated lab, properly fitted, working gas

pipe line, appropriate electrical system, concrete lab desk, sink and water tap properly fitted and continuous water supply.

3. Only one school has separate balance room and demonstration table which is in working condition.

4. One school has more than one exit rest two school have one exit only.

5. There is three Exhaust fans in CHGS, one exhaust fan in Varanasi Public School and Swami Harsevanand Public School lacks of exhaust fan.

Lab Equipment:

1. All three school have Bunsen burner, reagent self and common lab equipment such as test tube, beaker, conical flask, wire gauze, glass rod etc.

2. Only one school has fume cup board for experiment which release poisonous gas.

Teacher's monitoring and student's behavior:

1. Among three only two school's teachers monitor lab activity regularly.

2. Only one school teacher demonstrates the concern experiment on the demonstration table.

3. In all three school students follow teacher's instruction and use labeled chemicals.

Safety equipment:

1. Safety equipment not accessible to students in all three schools.

2. First aid kit is not available in all three schools.

3. There are three fire extinguishers in CHGS, one fire extinguisher in Varanasi Public School and Swami Harsewanand Public School.

4.2 ASSESSMENT OF PRACTICES OF SAFETY MEASURES:

For it following hypothesis was formulated and tested "There is no significant difference between the practices of safety measures of male and female senior secondary students." The result of analyzed data in accordance to Assessment of practices of Safety Measures is shown in table number 4.1 in which mean SD, Sample size, Degree of freedom (df) and t value are quoted:

Table no. 4.1

Item	Variables	No.	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Level of significance
							0.05
Practices of safety measures	Male	162	13.10	5.590	273	4.420	Not significant
	Female	113	15.81	3.991			

INTERPRETATION:

On the basis of statistical data visualized in table 4.1 there is significant difference between the practices of safety measures of male and female senior secondary students. It is because of the table t at significant level 0.05 degree of freedom 273 is -4.420. Thus the null hypothesis H_0 "There is no significant difference between the practices of safety measures of male and female senior secondary students" is rejected.

DISCUSSION:

In the above table no.4.1 it is obvious that there is role of gender in the practices of safety measures. So we can say that female students are more follow practices of safety measures.

- **Assessment of practices of Safety Measures:**

For it following hypothesis was formulated and tested "There is no significant difference between the practices of safety measures of class XI and class XII of senior secondary students." The result of analyzed data in accordance to Assessment of practices of Safety Measures is shown in table number 4.1 in which mean SD, Sample size, Degree of freedom (df) and t value are quoted:

Table no.4.2

Item	Variables	No.	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Level of significance
							0.05
Practices of safety measures	Class XI	174	13.24	5.443	273	4.237	Not significant
	Class XII	101	15.89	4.154			

INTERPRETATION:

On the basis of statistical data visualized in table 4.2 there is significant difference between the practices of safety measures of class XI and XII of senior secondary students. It is because of the table t at significant level 0.05 degree of freedom 273 is 4.237. Thus the null hypothesis H_0 "There is no significant difference between the practices of safety measures of class XI and XII of senior secondary students" is rejected.

DISCUSSION:

In the above table no.4.2 it is obvious that there is role of class level in the practices of safety measures. So, we can say that class XII students are more follow practices of safety measures.

Awareness of safety measures:

For it following hypothesis was formulated and tested "There is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of male and female of senior secondary students." The result of analyzed data in accordance to Assessment of Awareness of safety Measures is shown in table number 4.3 in which mean SD, Sample size, Degree of freedom (df) and t value are quoted:

Table no.4.3

Item	Variables	No.	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Level of significance
							0.05
Awareness of safety measures	Male	162	5.98	2.087	273	-1.636	Significant
	Female	113	6.39	1.957			

INTERPRETATION:

On the basis of statistical data visualized in table 4.3 there is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of male and female senior secondary students. It is because of the table t at significant level 0.05 degree of freedom 273 is -1.636. Thus the null hypothesis H_0 "There is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of male and female senior secondary students" is accepted.

DISCUSSION:

In the above table no.4.3 it is obvious that there is no role of gender in awareness of safety measures. So we can say that we should not be biased in deciding the level

of awareness of female and male; because the level of awareness of safety measures of male and female are nearly the same.

Awareness of safety measures:

For it following hypothesis was formulated and tested “There is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of class XI and XII of senior secondary students.” The result of analyzed data in accordance to Assessment of Awareness of safety Measures is shown in table number 4.4 in which mean SD, Sample size, Degree of freedom (df) and t value are quoted:

Table no. 4.4

Item	Variables	No.	Mean	Sd	Df	t-value	Level of significance
							0.05
Awareness of safety measures	Class XI	174	6.44	1.943	273	3.117	Not significant
	Class XII	101	5.67	2.119			

INTERPRETATION:

On the basis of statistical data visualized in table 4.4 there is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of class XI and XII senior secondary students. It is because of the table t at significant level 0.05 degree of freedom 273 is 3.117. Thus the null hypothesis H_0 “There is no significant difference between the awareness of safety measures of class XI and XII senior secondary students” is rejected.

DISCUSSION:

In the above table no.4.4 it is obvious that there is role of class level in awareness of safety measures. So we can say that level of awareness about the lab safety measures of class XI students is more than class XII.

Observation of Practices of Safety Measures Adopted While Doing Practical in Chemistry Laboratory:

The third objective of the study was “To observe the practices of safety measures adopted by senior secondary school students while doing practical in the Chemistry

laboratory.”

For the above purpose the researcher observed three schools Central Hindu Girls School, Varanasi Public School and Swami Harsevanand Public School with the help of observation schedule “Practices of Safety Measures Adopted While Doing Practical in Chemistry Laboratory” developed by the researcher. The Observation Schedule was divided into 5 domains namely-

1. Safety and dress rule.
2. Use of first aid kit.
3. Waste disposal
4. To follow common laboratory instruction:
5. Report undesirable activity and injury.

DOMAIN WISE DESCRIPTION OF OBSERVATION:

1. Safety and dress rule:

In all three school's students don't wear apron and shoes. All three school's students know how to dilute acid/base, clean apparatus before and after experiment but don't wash their hand with soap after experiment.

In all three school's students touch chemicals with bare hand and even don't know smelling chemical and vapour properly.

2. Use of First Aid Kit:

First aid kit is not available in all three schools that is why no chance of use of first aid kit at appropriate place in appropriate manner.

3. Waste disposal

All three schools lack of glass disposal box. In all three school student dispose liquid waste in to the sink and even don't allow water to run for some time by opening the tap. Corrosive chemicals is spilled and don't wash it off with water.

4. To follow common laboratory instruction:

All three school's students listen teacher's instruction carefully and do only assign experiment. In two school's students heat beakers/china dish on flame directly. In two school's students don't know proper way of boiling chemicals in test tube.

5. Report undesirable activity and injury:

In all three school students never report breakage of glass ware, lab apparatus and minor injuries.

RESULTS:

The statistically analysis of the data had led to the following results-

1. Provisions for the safety in the chemistry laboratory were not found in accordance with the recommended CBSE norms.
2. The level of awareness of safety measures of senior secondary school students in the chemistry laboratory was found to be low.
3. The practices of safety measures adopted by the senior secondary school students revealed poor experimental techniques.
4. It was found that senior secondary school students had poor knowledge about identified emergency facilities and equipments.
5. The male and female students of the senior secondary school of CBSE board included in this study were not found to differ significantly on the level of awareness about lab safety measures.
6. The senior secondary students of class XI and XII included in this study were found to differ significantly on the level of awareness about lab safety measures. Level of awareness about lab safety measures class XI students perform better than class XII students.

CONCLUSIONS:

upon:

The following conclusions have been drawn from the results and discussions are there

1. Study shows that the physical facilities in the chemistry laboratory are not found in accordance with the recommended CBSE norms. In other words physical facilities in the chemistry laboratory should be made in accordance with the recommended CBSE norms.
2. Study shows that level of awareness of safety measures of senior secondary student in the chemistry laboratory was found to be low. In other words level of awareness of safety measures in the chemistry laboratory must be improved.
3. Study shows that practices of safety measures adopted by senior secondary school students reveal poor experimental techniques. In other words for the improvement in practices of the safety measures students need to learn better experimental techniques.
4. Study shows that senior secondary school students had poor knowledge about emergency facilities and equipment. In other words senior secondary school students should aware more about emergency facilities and equipment.

5. Study shows that the male and female students of the senior secondary school of CBSE board included in this study were not found to differ significantly on the level of awareness about lab safety measures. In other words gender doesn't affect level of awareness about lab safety measures.

6. Study shows that the senior secondary students of class XI and XII included in this study were found to differ significantly on the level of awareness about lab safety measures. In other words level of class affect level of awareness about lab safety measures.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION:

Support for laboratory safety programs is the responsibility of school system administration. School system administration should appreciate the need for establishing safety and health instruction as a fundamental part of science curriculum and should operate their schools in as safe a manner as possible.

Teachers must have an obligation to instruct their students in the basic safety practices required in science laboratories. They also have an obligation to instruct them in the basic principles of health hazards that are found in most middle and senior secondary school science chemistry laboratories. Instructors must provide safety information and training to the students for every stage of experiment planning and be there to observe, supervise, instruct and correct during the experimentation. Teachers play the most important role in insuring a safe and healthful learning environment for the students. The ideal time to impress on students' minds the need for caution and preparation is before and while they are working with chemicals in science laboratory.

Students develop attitude towards safety and acquires habits of assessing hazards and risks when they are young. Students come from diverse backgrounds and have various level of preparation. Most of them have no previous hands on training in handling chemicals; others may come well repapered to assume personal responsibility for risk assessment and safety planning in their experiments. Safety and health training lays the foundation for acquiring these skills. The students should think through implications and experiments that they observe or conduct in order to learn that safe procedures are part of the way science must be done. Students may find a discussion of taxonomy interesting, informative and beneficial.

All safety programs must actively involve the school administrators, supervisors, teachers, students and all have the responsibility for safety and health of every other person in the laboratory and school.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH:

India is developing country. Its progress can be improved by the improvement of the educational institution for this purpose knowledge of perspective and practicing teacher is essential. The present study and its finding will serve as base for implementation of new more advance research in future by person of fertile imagination and competence. Hence in the view of finding, some of suggestion for further research which can be gain fully utilized have been given below.

1. The present study was conducted on the sample taken from CBSE schools of Varanasi district only. For verification of this result a similar study can be conducted in other CBSE schools of the India.

2. A similar study can be conducted on large sample to insure generalization and comprehension.

3. A similar study can be conducted on state board and ICSE board school also.

4. A similar study can be conducted on secondary level and university level also.

5. A similar study can be conducted on other subjects such as physics, biology also.

6. A comparative study can be conducted on rural and urban CBSE and state board schools also.

7. A comparative study can be conducted on CBSE and ICSE schools.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STYUDY:

Rossmann and Rallies (2003) once remarked that “No studies are perfect.” This study also had limitation, which the investigator would like to mention. These limitations are:

1. Larger group of students could not be taken because of the paucity of time and resources.

2. This study is restricted to only senior secondary CBSE schools.

3. For this study, some data has been collected by the use of self-reported measure, in the form of questionnaire, which has in own inherent limitation.

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